

Liquid-liquid extraction and separation of barium from associated elements using dibenzo-24-crown-8

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Manuscript received 13 September 1999, revised 14 February 2000, accepted 28 April 2000

A simple extractive separation method for trace level of barium (2.5–25 ppm) has been developed using dibenzo-24-crown-8 from picric acid medium. Barium is quantitatively extracted from 0.008–0.05 M picric acid with 0.0008–0.01 M dibenzo-24-crown-8 in nitrobenzene as a diluent. From the organic phase barium is quantitatively stripped with 1–10 M HNO₃ and HClO₄, 1–8 M HBr, 0.1–2.0 M HCl. Separation of barium has been carried out from a number of binary and multicomponent mixtures. The method is extended for the determination of barium in various rock samples.

β -Diketo liquid chelating exchanger (RCOCH₂COCF₃) has been applied previously for separation of barium from associated elements¹. Some efforts were made to use crown ethers for the solvent extraction separation studies of barium. The separation of barium from other alkaline earths was achieved but for such separation other extractants along with dibenzo-18-crown-6 and 18-crown-6 were employed². The stability of strontium and barium has been reported with 18-crown-6 from picrate solution³. The substoichiometric ion-pair extraction of barium with cryptand-2.2.2 and 18-crown-6 has also been carried out using picrate as a counter anion⁴. Spectrophotometric investigation of complex formation of barium and calcium with aza-15-crown-5 has been reported⁵. Synergic extraction studies of barium with dicarbonylcobaltate with various crown ethers have been carried out⁶. Phosphoryl containing podand showed high selectivity for barium⁷ than other alkali and alkaline earths from picrate extraction studies.

The present communication reports the results of solvent extraction separation studies of barium and its separation from the associated elements using dibenzo-24-crown-8 in picrate medium. The method has also been extended for the determination of barium in number of real samples.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of barium was studied at varied picric acid concentrations (0.00001–0.05 M), using 0.001 M of various crown ethers in nitrobenzene as the diluent. The results show that with 15C5 and B15C5 barium is quantitatively (100%) extracted from 0.004–0.05 M picric acid. With 18C6 the extraction of barium was not quantitative – 68% extraction of barium at 0.05 M picric acid. The extraction of barium was quantitative with B18C6, DC18C6 and

DB24C8 at 0.008–0.05 M picric acid. With DB18C6 the extraction of barium was quantitative at 0.01–0.05 M picric acid. With DC24C8 barium was quantitatively extracted from 0.004–0.05 M picric acid. Since 15C5, B15C5, B18C6, DB18C6, DC18C6, DB24C8 and DC24C8 showed quantitative extraction of barium, the use of DB24C8 was preferred over other crown ethers for further studies as it has almost no solubility in aqueous phase and thus enabling repeated use by regenerating with 2 M HNO₃. Although other crown ethers showed quantitative extraction of barium but have partial solubility in the aqueous phase, hence their reuse is precluded.

Effect of dibenzo-24-crown-8 concentration : In order to ascertain the optimum concentration of DB24C8 for the quantitative extraction of barium, extractions were carried out from 0.01 M picric acid by varying the concentration of DB24C8 in the concentration range 0.000001–0.01 M using nitrobenzene as a diluent. Barium was extracted to the extent of 21% at 0.000001 M. The extraction of barium increased with increase in DB24C8 concentration. The extraction was 25% at 0.00001 M and 76% at 0.0001 M. Barium extraction was quantitative (100%) from 0.0008–0.01 M. Further extraction studies of barium were carried out using 10 ml of 0.001 M DB24C8 in nitrobenzene.

Choice of diluents : The extraction of barium was studied using 0.01 M picric acid with 0.001 M DB24C8 with various solvents such as benzene, toluene, xylene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane, dichloroethane, tetrachloroethane and nitrobenzene. The phase volume ratio was maintained to unity. The studies revealed that the extraction of barium was 18% with benzene, 5% with toluene, 15% with xylene, 20% with

chloroform, 19% with dichloromethane, 50% with dichloroethane and 22% with tetrachloroethane. The extraction of barium was quantitative (100%) only with nitrobenzene. Hence further extraction studies of barium were carried out from nitrobenzene as the diluent.

Choice of stripping agents : After extraction barium was stripped from the organic phase with various stripping agents, such as nitric acid, hydrochloric acid, hydrobromic acid, perchloric acid and acetic acid in the concentration range 0.01–10 *M* (and 0.1–8 *M* in case of HBr). The stripping of barium was quantitative with 1–10 *M* HNO₃ and HClO₄, 1–8 *M* HBr and 0.1–2 *M* HCl. Acetic acid was found to be an inefficient strippant for barium in the concentration range 0.1–10 *M*. For further studies 2 *M* HNO₃ was used as the strippant.

Separation of Ba from binary mixtures : Barium was extracted in the presence of other ions. Amongst *s*-block elements, sodium, potassium and cesium showed partial extraction along with barium, thus showing low tolerance limit. Rubidium was quantitatively extracted along with barium. Lithium and other alkaline earth metal ions were not extracted and showed very high tolerance limit. Amongst *p*-block elements, lead(II) showed partial extraction along with barium. Most of the *p*-block and *d*-block cations were tolerated in high proportions. The anions of inorganic and organic acids were tolerated in higher concentrations. The tolerance limits (in mg) are as follows : Pb^{II}, Cs^I, 0.1; Na^I, 0.2; K^I, Rb^I, 0.25; Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, 0.5; Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, W^{VI}, Tl^{III}, 1.0; V^V, Be^{II}, 2; Mo^{VI}, 4.5; Sr^{II}, Co^{II}, Sb^{III}, U^{VI}, 5; Cu^{II}, 5.5; Hg^{II}, Al^{III}, Th^{IV}, 7; La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Ga^{III}, 10; Li^I, In^{III}, 30; Mg^{II}, 35; Ca^{II}, 50.

Separation of Ba in multicomponent mixtures : Barium was extracted from 0.01 *M* picric acid with 0.001 *M* DB24C8 as well as with 0.001 *M* DB18C6 in nitrobenzene as diluent. Under the set conditions there was no extraction of Mo^{VI} but from 8 *M* HCl there was quantitative extraction of Mo^{VI} with DB18C6 in nitrobenzene whereas barium was not extracted. This behavior exhibited by DB24C8 and DB18C6 with different anions was exploited for the separation of barium, molybdenum and other ions in multicomponent mixtures.

From a mixture of molybdenum(VI), barium(II) and X (X = Li^I, Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Y^{III}, Th^{IV}), Mo^{VI} was separated by extracting from 8 *M* HCl with 0.001 *M* DB18C6, while barium and X remained in the aqueous phase. After evaporating the aqueous phase it was treated with water and barium was extracted with 0.001 *M* DB24C8 from 0.01 *M* picric acid leaving behind X in the aqueous phase. Molybdenum(VI) and barium from the respective organic phases were stripped with 2 *M* nitric acid.

From a mixture of uranium(VI), barium(II) and X, U^{VI} was separated by extracting from 8 *M* HCl with 0.001 *M* DB24C8, while barium and X remained in the aqueous phase. After evaporating the aqueous phase it was treated with water and barium was extracted with 0.001 *M* DB24C8 from 0.01 *M* picric acid leaving behind X in the aqueous phase. Uranium(VI) and barium from the respective organic phases were stripped with 2 *M* nitric acid.

Application : The proposed method was applied for determination of barium in standard rock samples such as, KC-11, KC-12 (King's College, London) and Syenite rock (SY-II) (Canadian Std.). The samples were brought into solution by following the procedure described earlier⁸. An aliquot of sample solution was treated as per the general procedure and the barium content determined. The amount of barium found in KC-11 rock sample was 485 ppm against the reported value of 491 ppm and in KC-12 rock sample 1610 ppm against the reported value of 1600 ppm. In syenite rock sample barium was found to be 465 ppm against the reported value of 460 ppm. In basaltic-BR sample the barium was found to be 1045 ppm against the reported value of 1050 ppm. These results reveal that the proposed method can conveniently be used to analyse barium from rock samples.

Experimental

A Zeiss spectrophotometer (Spekol-10), a digital pH meter (Elico LI-120) with glass and calomel electrodes, and a digital flame photometer (PEI, 041) were used.

A stock solution of barium (1.00 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving barium nitrate (AnalaR) in distilled deionised water and standardized gravimetrically⁹ and a 100 µg/ml of barium solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. Solutions of crown ethers were prepared from 15-crown-5, benzo-15-crown-5, 18-crown-6, benzo-18-crown-6, dibenzo-18-crown-6, dicyclohexano-18-crown-6, dibenzo-24-crown-8, dicyclohexano-24-crown-8 (Aldrich) without further purification. Picric acid solution (0.05 *M*) was prepared in distilled deionised water.

Procedure : To an aliquot of a solution containing 100 µg barium, picric acid was added so as to have a concentration of 0.00001–0.05 *M* in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution was then equilibrated with 10 ml of 0.001 *M* suitable crown ether with nitrobenzene as the diluent, for 10 min. Barium stripped from the organic phase with 2 *M* nitric acid (10 ml) was determined spectrophotometrically with Sulfonazo-III at 640 nm¹⁰. The concentration of barium was calculated from a calibration graph.

Note

References

- 1 S R Dan (Biswas) and A K Das, *Fresenius Z Anal Chem*, 1988, **331**, 826
- 2 B S Mohite and S M Khopkar, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1988, **206**, 363
- 3 Y Hasegawa and H Date, *Solv Extn Ion Exchange*, 1988, **6**, 431
- 4 T Fukaya, H Imura and N Suzuki, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1993, **272**, 279
- 5 N Mateeva, V Enchev and M Mitewa, *J Incl Phenom Mol Recogn Chem*, 1995, **20**, 323 M Mitewa, N Mateeva, L Antonov and T Deligeorgiev, *Dyes Pigm*, 1995 **27** 219
- 6 P Venura, *J Radioanal Nucl Chem*, 1998, **228** 43 P Venura and E Makilik, *J Radioanal Nucl Chem* 1998, **237** 11
- 7 A Y Nazarenko, V E Baulin, J D Lamb, T A Volkova, A A Varnek and G Wipff, *Solv Extn Ion Exchange*, 1999, **17**, 495
- 8 B S Mohite and S M Khopkar, *Talanta* 1985, **32** 565
- 9 A I Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1975
- 10 P J Kemp and M B Williams, *Anal Chem*, 1973 **45**, 124

